

A modified Equation for the Viscosity of Dilute Solutions of the Strong Electrolytes and Quantitative Treatment of its *B*-Coefficient

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Jones and Dole's equation for the viscosity of dilute solutions of the strong electrolytes has been modified in previous publications. The modified equation has been subjected to further test in this paper using a number of strong electrolytes and has been found satisfactory. An expression for the *B*-coefficient of the modified equation has been derived in this paper on the assumption that it should be identified with $2.5 \bar{V}$ of the Einstein viscosity equation, where $\bar{V}$ is the volume fraction per unit concentration (molar scale) of the electrolyte. This equation has been subjected to test using a number of strong electrolytes and has been found satisfactory. It has also been shown that the partial molal entropy of hydration $\bar{S}_h^0$ of an electrolyte in aqueous solution varies linearly with $(h - \phi/18)$, where h is the hydration number, and $\phi/18$, the volume fraction of the electrolyte.

THE viscosity equation of Jones and Dole¹ may be expressed as

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

where, η is the viscosity of the solution of the electrolyte and η_0 that of the pure solvent at a given temperature, A and B are constants and C the molar concentration. The term $A\sqrt{C}$ has been attributed to interionic attraction^{1,2}. It has been shown in previous publications^{3,4} that this term should be replaced by $g(C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2})$ and the modified equation should be written as

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + g(C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}) + BC \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), g , C_0 and B are constants, g contains $\sqrt{a}$, a being the 'effective ionic diameter'[†] and it can be calculated from theory if a is known, C_0 represents that concentration of the electrolyte at which inter-ionic attraction disappears. It is very small but not zero.

In this paper, equation (2) has been subjected to test using fresh electrolytes and the results are recorded in Table 1. The effects of electrical charge and hydration of ions on B of equation (1) have been discussed by a number of authors⁵⁻⁸. Gurney⁷ and Nightingale⁸ have shown that there is a linear relationship between the *B*-coefficient and the partial molal entropies of the hydrated ions in aqueous solution. Since *B*-coefficient of equation (1) differs from that of equation (2) so fresh investigation has been undertaken to ascertain if the aforesaid relationship holds good in the latter case also. Besides this, the existence of a direct relationship

between the partial molal entropy of the electrolyte in solution and $(h - \phi/18)$, where h is the hydration number and $\phi/18$, the volume fraction of the electrolyte has also been investigated. The results are recorded in Table 2.

It may be mentioned that both Gurney⁷ and Nightingale⁸ partitioned the *B*-coefficient and the partial molal entropy of the electrolyte between the constituent ions and used them in their investigations. As these procedures involve assumptions which may be questioned, so we avoided them and used in our investigation the partial molal entropy and the viscosity *B*-coefficient of the molecule of the electrolyte in solution. The results are recorded in Tables 2-7. It appears from the data recorded in Tables 2-6 that the following linear relationships hold good,

$$\bar{S}^0 = m(B) + C \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{S}_h^0 = m_0(B) + C_0 \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{S}^0 = m_1(h - \phi/18) + C_1 \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{S}_h^0 = m_2(h - \phi/18) + C_2 \quad (6)$$

In equation (3), $\bar{S}^0$ represents the partial molal entropy of the electrolyte in solution found from the data recorded in Gurney's work⁷ and m and C are constants. In equation (4), $\bar{S}_h^0$ represents the partial molal entropy of hydration of the electrolyte in solution found from Fig. 5 of Nightingale's paper⁸. In equations (5) and (6), $\bar{S}^0$ and $\bar{S}_h^0$ are the same as in the equations (3) and (4), h and $\phi/18$ have the same significance as stated already and m_1 ,

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† Errata in previous paper⁴ footnote p. 191, Read $mG=116.19$ for KBr instead of 11610.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF η/η_0 WITH ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of η/η_0		C	Values of η/η_0	
		Obs.	Calcd.		Obs.	Calcd.
AgNO ₃ , ^a Eqn. (2) g=0.002 6 C ₀ ^{1/2} =0.025 B=0.054	0.002	1.000 36	1.000 37	0.02	1.001 77	1.001 72
	0.005	1.000 68	1.000 66	0.05	1.003 64	1.003 59
	0.01	1.001 10	1.001 14	0.1	1.006 52	1.006 55
CsNO ₃ , ^b Eqn. (2) g=0.001 7 C ₀ ^{1/2} =0.03 B=-0.084	0.000 5	1.000 03	1.000 05	0.005	0.999 86	0.999 84
	0.001	1.000 03	1.000 04	0.01	0.999 52	0.999 51
	0.002	1.000 00	1.000 01	0.02	0.998 76	0.998 77
CsI, ^c Eqn. (2) g=0.001 1 C ₀ ^{1/2} =0.029 B=-0.114	0 000 997	1.000 03	0.999 94	0.019 92	0.998 15	0.998 00
	0.004 99	0.999 63	0.999 56	0.049 99	0.994 78	0.994 70
	0.009 97	0.999 11	0.999 05	0.099 66	0.989 10	0.989 15
KClO ₃ , ^b Eqn. (2) g=0.002 C ₀ ^{1/2} =0.023 B=-0.023	0.002	1.000 17	1.000 16	0.02	1.000 11	1.000 04
	0.005	1.000 21	1.000 18	0.05	0.999 57	0.999 57
	0.01	1.000 17	1.000 16	0.1	0.998 50	0.998 58
KBrO ₃ , ^b Eqn. (2) g=0.002 4 C ₀ ^{1/2} =0.015 B=0.006	0.002	1.000 26	1.002 8	0.02	1.000 77	1.000 73
	0.005	1.000 48	1.000 41	0.05	1.001 25	1.001 18
	0.01	1.000 59	1.000 54	0.1	1.001 76	1.001 73

^a Ref. 9. ^b Ref. 10. ^c Ref. 11.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF S^0 AND $\bar{S}_h^0$ WITH B-COEFFICIENT OF SOME ALKALI HALIDES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	B-Coefficient	Values of $\bar{S}^{0a}$		Values of $\bar{S}_h^{0b}$	
			Obs.	Calcd. Eqn. (3)	Obs.	Calcd. Eqn. (4)
Eqn. (3) m = -140 C = 38.8	LiCl	0.142	18.2	18.9	44.6	44.5
	LiBr	0.119	24.3	22.1	41.6	42.5
	LiI	0.08	30.0	27.6	38.7	39.3
	NaCl	0.086	27.5	26.8	41.0	39.9
Eqn. (4) m ₀ = 84.4 C ₀ = 32.5	KCl	-0.008	37.0	40.0	32.7	31.8
	KBr	-0.044	43.8	45.0	39.7	28.8
	KI	-0.08	49.5	50.0	26.2	25.7
	CsI	-0.114	57.1	54.8	22.8	22.9

^a Ref. 7. ^b Ref. 8.

C_1 , m_0 and C_0 are constants. In view of the afore-said linear relationships it is considered desirable to investigate if there is any relationship between B and $(h-\phi/18)$. An attempt has been made in the following way. Let us accept Frank and Wen's model⁹ of hydrated ions consisting of three zones—zone (1) in which the ion is firmly bound to h water molecules incontact with zone (2) in which the structure of water is disturbed and this latter in contact with zone (3) in which the normal water structure prevails. Let us next put $B=2.5 \bar{V}$, where $\bar{V}$ is the volume fraction per unit concentration of the viscosity equation of Einstein. The following equation is now set up,

$$\bar{V} = [(18h - y\phi) + x(\phi - \phi_{kcl})]/1000 \quad (7)$$

In equation (7), $(18h - y\phi)$ represents the proportionate contribution of hydration of the ions to $\bar{V}$, assuming that owing to electrostriction and increased compactness of packing $18h$ is reduced by the amount $y\phi$ where y is a constant and $x(\phi - \phi_{kcl})$ represents similar contribution of zone (2) to $\bar{V}$, where x is a constant and ϕ_{kcl} the apparent molar volume of KCl taken as standard of reference. In equation (7) 1000 occurs because C is expressed in molar scale.

We may now write down the following equation,

$$B = 0.045[h - (y-x)\phi/18 - x\phi_{kcl}/18] \quad (7a)$$

When equation (7a) is subjected to test using a few 1 : 1 electrolyte, for which B , h and ϕ are known, it

is found that, $y=2$ and $x=1$. Equation (7a) may now be expressed in the following simplified form,

$$B=0.045[h-(\phi+\phi_{\text{cal}})/18] \quad (7b)$$

Equation (7b) should hold good for all 1 : 1 electrolytes containing monoatomic ions. It is also found to hold good for simple polyatomic ions, like the nitrates which can be treated as spherical in shape. The validity or otherwise of equations (2) to (7b), have been considered critically in the 'Discussion' section.

Processing of the data recorded in the Tables :

Under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the equations used and the values of their constants. The electrolytes selected and the source of the relevant data indicated by ref. (abbreviation for reference numbers) are also mentioned under this head in some tables, C , where it occurs, represents molar concentration and the value of ϕ used is the same as that at $C=0.1 M$, since the highest concentration up to which the equations have been used is $0.1 M$.

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the values of η/η_0 calculated by using equation (2) agree well with those observed for the electrolytes selected. Taking into consideration these results along with those published previously it may be concluded that the validity of equation (2) has been established beyond doubt. The B -coefficient of equation (2) differs from that of equation (1). Even then the data recorded in Tables 2 and 3 show that they vary linearly with both $\bar{S}_h^0$ and $\bar{S}_h^p$. The agreement of Nightingale's data with $\bar{S}_h^0$ is better than that of Gurney's data with $\bar{S}_h^0$. It may be pointed out that according to Nightingale's data recorded in Tables 2 and 3, the values of m_0 and c_0

of the straight line representing the alkali halides differ from that of the straight line representing the nitrates. Hence, Nightingale's claim that the relationship between $\bar{S}_h^0$ and the B -coefficients of different electrolytes can be represented by a single straight line is questionable.

The data recorded in Table 4 show that both $\bar{S}_h^0$ and $\bar{S}_h^p$ vary linearly with $(h-\phi/18)$ for the chlorides of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ and Cs^+ .

It may now be mentioned that equation (7b) may be derived in ways other than the one discussed already. Substituting the values, recorded in Tables 2 and 4, of m and c into equation (3) and of m_1 and c_1 into equation (5), we may write as

$$\bar{S}^0 = -140(B) + 38.8 \quad (3a)$$

and

$$\bar{S}^p = -6.2(h-\phi/18) + 46.7 \quad (5a)$$

Combination of equations (3a) and (5a) with the elimination of $\bar{S}^0$ yields the following equation,

$$B=0.044[(h-\phi/18) - 1.3] \quad (7c)$$

It will be noticed that equation (7c) is the same as equation (7b), the slight differences in the values of the constants are to be attributed to experimental error in the determination of B and $\bar{S}^0$.

Similarly, substituting the data on m_0 , c_0 and m_2 , c_2 recorded in Tables 2 and 4 into equations (4) and (6), we get the following equations,

$$\bar{S}_h^0 = 84.4(B) + 32.5 \quad (4a)$$

and

$$\bar{S}_h^p = 3.8(h-\phi/18) + 27.0 \quad (6a)$$

Combination of equations (4a) and (6a) with the elimination of $\bar{S}_h^p$ yields the following equation,

$$B=0.045[(h-\phi/18) - 1.44] \quad (7d)$$

Equation (7d) is the same as equation (7b).

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF $\bar{S}_h^0$ WITH B -COEFFICIENT OF THE NITRATES OF Ag^+ , K^+ AND Cs^+

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	B -coefficient	Values of $\bar{S}_h^0$	
			Obs.	Calcd.
Ref. 8	AgNO_3	+0.054	49.9	49.8
Eqn. (4)	KNO_3	-0.047	34.1	33.7
$m_0=100$ $C_0=38.4$	CsNO_3	-0.084	30.1	30.0

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF $\bar{S}^0$ AND $\bar{S}_h^p$ WITH $(h-\phi/18)$ OF THE CHLORIDES OF Li^+ , K^+ AND Cs^+

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	$(h-\phi/18)$	Values of $\bar{S}^0$ ^a		Values of $\bar{S}_h^p$ ^b	
			Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd. Eqn. (6)
Ref. 12	LiCl	4.63	18.2	18.0	44.6	44.6
Eqn. (5)	NaCl	3.14	27.5	27.3	39.8	38.9
$m_1=-6.2$ $C_1=46.7$	KCl	1.47	37.7	37.6	31.8	32.6
Eqn. (6)	CsCl	0.2	45.3	45.5	28.6	27.8
$m_2=3.8$ $C_2=27.0$						

^a Ref. 7.

^b Ref. 8

It may, therefore, be concluded that equation (7b) should hold good for all the electrolytes recorded in Tables 2-5 since they are all covered by equations (3), (4), (5) and (6). Data which have not been recorded here also show that it holds good for NH_4Cl , KClO_3 and KBrO_3 . An important use of equation (7b) would be the estimation of the hydration number h , of the strong electrolytes containing simple ions which can be treated as spherical. In Tables 6 and 7 are recorded the values of h of some of the common electrolytes. It will be noticed that the calculated values agree well with those found from other sources. For the 1 : 1 electrolytes as already mentioned $y=2$ and $x=1$, and so equation (7a) assumes the simple form of equation (7b) which has been used. In the case of the 2 : 1 electrolytes, it has been assumed that in equation (7a), $y=4$ and $x=1$ and the following equation has been used,

$$B = 0.045[(h - \phi/18) - 1.5] \quad (7.1)$$

The data on BaCl_2 recorded in Table 7 seems to fit equation (7.1) well.

Further investigation on the determination of h of the ion of different strong electrolytes using data on their mean activity coefficient at high concentration, as indicated by Glueckauf¹³, is desirable. It may be mentioned that Stokes and Robinson¹⁴ have given preference to Glueckauf's method over that of others for reasons discussed in their paper.

Mention has already been made that according to data recorded in Table 2, both $\bar{S}^\circ$ and $\bar{S}_h^\circ$ vary linearly with B . Hence by eliminating B , the following linear relation can be established between them,

$$\bar{S}^\circ = -1.66 \bar{S}_h^\circ + 92.8 \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, the data recorded in Table 4 show that for equation (5), the ratio of the constants $c_1/m_1 = -46.2/6.2 = -7.45$, and for equation (6), $c_2/m_2 = 7.1$. They are to be identified with $\pm R$ in $[(\phi_{\text{KCl}}/18)/1000/18] = \mp 7.2$ and may be considered, as has been done by Gurney⁷ to be related to the 'cratic part' of the entropies $\bar{S}^\circ$ and $\bar{S}_h^\circ$. Thus, the aforesaid ratios of the constants of the equations (5) and (6) can be found theoretically.

TABLE 5—VARIATION OF $\bar{S}_h^\circ$ WITH $(h - \phi/18)$ OF THE NITRATES OF Ag^+ , K^+ AND Cs^+

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	B-coefficient	$(h - \phi/18)$	Values of $\bar{S}_h^\circ$	
				Obs.	Calcd.
Eqn. (6) ^a	AgNO_3	+0.054	2.7	49.9	44.0
$m_2=4.5$	KNO_3	-0.047	0.45	34.1	39.8
$C_2=31.8$	CsNO_3	-0.084	-0.37	30.1	30.1

^a Ref. 8.

TABLE 6—VALUES OF h OF A FEW 1 : 1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	B-coefficient	$\phi/18$	$(h - \phi/18)$	Values of h found from	
					Eqn. (7)	Other sources
Ref. 4	LiCl	0.142	0.97	4.64	5.6	5.63 ^a
Eqn. (7b)	LiBr	0.119	1.86	4.17	5.5	5.29 ^b
	LiI	0.08	1.99	3.39	5.3	5.11 ^b
	NaCl	0.086	0.95	3.44	4.4	4.1 ^a
	KCl	-0.008	1.53	1.35	2.9	3.0 ^a
	KBr	-0.044	1.9	0.59	2.4	2.66 ^b
	KI	-0.081	2.55	-0.27	2.3	2.62 ^b
	CsCl	-0.052	2.21	0.38	2.6	2.4 ^a
	NH_4Cl	-0.007	2.02	1.36	3.4	
	KNO_3	-0.047	2.17	0.49	2.6	
	AgNO_3	0.054	1.6	2.73	4.9	

^a Ref. 12. ^b Ref. 13.

TABLE 7—VALUES OF h OF SOME 2 : 1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	Electrolyte	B-coefficient	$\phi/18$	$(h - \phi/18)$	Values of h found from	
					Eqn. (7.1)	Other sources
Ref. 4	BaCl_2	0.987	1.4	6.8	11.0	10.5 ^c
Eqn. (7.1)	K_2SO_4	0.211	2.1	6.2	12.5	

^a Ref. 12. ^b Ref. 13. ^c Ref. 14.

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